

Bambusiomyces, a new genus of smut fungi (*Ustilaginomycetes*)

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Abstract. A new genus of smut fungi, *Bambusiomyces* is proposed for *Ustilago shiraiana* on host plants in the tribe *Bambuseae* of *Poaceae*.

Key words: *Bambusiomyces*, *B. shiraianus*, new combination, new genus, smut fungi, taxonomy

Introduction

A smut fungus, *Ustilago shiraiana*, was described by Hennings (1901: 260) on the surface of young shoots of wild Japanese bamboo, *Bambusa veitchii* (= *Sasa veitchii*). Subsequently, the fungus was collected in China, Japan and SE Asia on members of *Arundinaria*, *Bambusa*, *Indocalamus*, *Phyllostachys*, *Pleioblastus*, *Sasa*, *Sasaella*, *Sasamorphia*, *Semiarundinaria* and *Sinarundinaria*, all belonging to the tribe *Bambuseae*, subfam. *Bambusoideae*, fam. *Poaceae* (Clayton & Renvoize 1986). The disease, called stem smut of bamboo, was also introduced into the USA from Japan (Patterson & Charles 1916). The fungus was studied by Hori (1907), who emended its description (comp. also Patterson & Charles 1916: 353). Mordue (1991) provided a review and illustrations of *U. shiraiana*.

Materials and methods

For the present work, the following specimens were examined, preserved in the author's collection 'H.U.V.' (Herbarium Ustilaginales Vánky). From China: HUV 7986, 12049, from Japan: HUV 4508, 4512, 11813, 11825, 13682, 16345, 16518, 16635, 16636, 16652, 16653, 16654, 16655, 21413, 21996, from Sri Lanka: HUV 4509, 4510, 4511, and from the USA: HUV 9911.

Sorus and spore characteristics were studied using dried herbarium specimens. To soften the tissues, pieces of mature sori were boiled in a mixture of distilled water and lactophenol with cotton blue, on a microscope slide, and then

hand sectioned with a razor blade under a stereo microscope. Thin sections, showing the structure of sori, were mounted in lactophenol with cotton blue on a slide, covered with a cover glass, gently heated to expand structures and expel air bubbles, and examined by a light microscope (LM) at 1000× magnification. For scanning electron microscopy (SEM), spores were placed on double-sided adhesive tape, mounted on a specimen stub, sputter-coated with gold-palladium, ca 20 nm, and examined in a SEM at 10 kV.

The nomenclatural novelties were registered in MycoBank (www.Mycobank.org, Crous *et al.* 2004).

Taxonomy

Based on host plant taxonomy, sorus and spore morphology, and the peculiar spore germination of *U. shiraiana*, a new genus is proposed for it:

Bambusiomyces Vánky, **gen. nov.**

MycoBank 563475

Sori ad superficiem plantarum trib. Bambuseae (Poaceae fam.), *atrobrunnei*, *pulverei tantum e sporis compositi, sine cellulis sterilibus*. *Sporae singulares, pigmentatae (brunneae, non violaceo nec rubro tinctae)*. *Sporae germinantes cum holobasidio brevi, apice basidiosporas ovoideas sive ellipsoideas producentes*.

Typus generis: *Bambusiomyces shiraianus*.

Sori on the surface of host plants in the tribe *Bambuseae* (*Poaceae*), dark brown, powdery, composed of spores only. **Sterile cells** absent. **Spores** single, pigmented (brown,

Fig. 1. Sori of *Bambusiomyces shiraianus* on the distal, shortened internodes of young branches of *Sasa veitchii* (type). Habit. Bar = 1 cm

without violet or red tint). **Spore germination** results in a short holobasidium producing apically ovoid or ellipsoidal basidiospores.

Bambusiomyces shiraianus (Henn.) Vánky, **comb. nov.**

Mycobank 563476

Basionym: *Ustilago shiraiana* Hennings, Bot. Jahrb. Syst. 28: 260, 1901. — Type on *Bambusa veitchii* (= *Sasa veitchii*), Japan, Nikko, Yumoto, VI.1899, Shirai, TNS; isotypes HBG, HUV 16635!

Contractia bambusae Miyabe & Hori, in Yoshino, Bot. Mag. Tokyo 19: 199, 1905. — Type on *Phyllostachys bambusoides* (= *Ph. reticulata*), Japan, Kyushu Island, Kumamoto, V.1905, leg. S. Okuyama (syn. by Hori 1907).

Sori (Fig. 1) surrounding the stems of shortened internodes of the young end-branches, partly concealed by leaf sheaths, often swollen. Sori also on both surfaces of the

proximal part of the leaf sheaths as striae between the veins, by confluence covering the entire distal leaf sheaths, also found at the top of the shoots in small, congested leaves. The fungus often produces witches' brooms, deformations and distortions. Infection systemic, the mycelium perennates in old stems. Spore mass blackish brown, semiagglutinated to powdery, produced on the surface of the host tissues (Figs 2–3). **Spores** (Figs 4–5) globoid, flattened, 4–5.5 μm wide, in face view circular or subcircular, rarely ovoid or elliptic, 5.5–7 \times 6.5–8 (–9) μm , pale yellowish brown; wall even, c. 0.5 μm thick, smooth, in SEM finely, densely verruculose. **Spore germination** (Fig. 6) results in a short, simple, rarely apically bifurcate, aseptate basidium, 3–5 \times 15–20 μm , apically producing ovoid or ellipsoidal basidiospores measuring 2.5–4 \times 3–9 μm .

On *Poaceae*: *Arundinaria* sp., *Bambusa* sp., *Indocalamus debilis* (Thwaites) Alston (*Arundinaria debilis* Thwaites), *I. tessellatus* (Munro) Keng. f. (*Bambusa tessellata* Munro), *Sasa tessellata* (Munro) Makino & Shibata), *Phyllostachys aurea* (Siebold) Carr. ex Rivière, *Ph. bambusoides* Siebold & Zucc. (*Ph. reticulata* K. Koch), *Ph. congesta* Redle, *Ph. edulis* Rivière & C. Rivière (*Ph. mites* Rivière var. *heterocycla* Makino), *Ph. henonis* Mitford., *Ph. heterocycla* (Carrière) Matsum. (*Bambusa heterocycla* Carrière), *Ph. heterocycla* var. *pubescens* Muroi, *Ph. makinoi* Hayata, *Ph. nigra* (Lodd. ex Lindl.) Munro (*Ph. puberula* Munro), *Ph. quillioi* Rivière & C. Rivière, *Ph. stauntonii* Munro, *Pleioblastus chino* (Franch. & Sav.) Makino (*Arundinaria chino* (Franch. & Sav.) Makino; *Pl. maximowiczii* A. & C. Rivière), *Pl. vaginatus* (Hack.) Nakai (*Arundinaria vaginata* Hack.), *Pl. simonii* (Carrière) Nakai (*Arundinaria simonii* (Carrière) Rivière & C. Rivière), *Sasa kurilensis* (Rupr.) Makino & Shibata, *S. nana* Makino (*Arundinaria paniculata* Makino), *S. nipponica* (Makino) Makino & Shibata, *S. senanensis* (Franch. & Savat.) Rehder (*S. paniculata* (Schmidt) Makino, Shibata & Nakai), *S. veitchii* (Carrière) Rehder (*Bambusa veitchii* Carrière; *Arundinaria veitchii* (Carrière) N.E. Br.; *S. albomarginata* Makino & Shibata), *Sasaella ramosa* Makino (*Sasa ramosa* (Makino) Makino & Shibata), *Sasamorpha borealis* (Hack.) Nakai (*Bambusa borealis* Hack.; *Sasa borealis* (Hack.) Makino & Shibata), *Semiarundinaria yashadake* (Makino) Makino, *Sinarundinaria wightiana* (Nees) Chao & Renv.

Geographic distribution: S & E Asia (China, India, Japan, Korea, Russian Far East, Sri Lanka, Taiwan), N America (USA). Comp. Fischer (1953: 294), Gandhe (2011: 358), Guo (2000: 82), Gutner (1941: 98), Kakishima (1982: 91), Mordue 1991: 63), Uljanishchev (1968: 21), Vánky (1979: 12, 2007: 197, 2012: 1268), Zundel (1953: 201).

Discussion

A similar smut fungus to *Bambusiomyces shiraianus* is *Ustilago hypodytes* (Schltdl.) Fries (1832: 518). It occurs on the surface of distal internodes of various grasses. This species was transferred into the genus *Tranzscheliella* by Vánky &

Figs 2–3. Transversal section of part of a sorus of *Bambusiomyces shiraianus* on the surface of *Indocalamus debilis* (Vánky, Ustil. exs. No. 171). Handcut sections in lactophenol with cotton blue. Bars = 10 μ m. **Figs 4–5.** Spores of *Bambusiomyces shiraianus* on *Sasa veitchii* (type) in LM and in SEM. Bars = 10 μ m

McKenzie (2002: 156). The type of the genus is *T. otophora* Lavrov (= *T. williamsii* (Griffiths) Dingley & Versluys) on *Stipa pennata* L., but also on *Achnatherum*, *Austrostipa*, *Oryzopsis* and other *Stipa* species. *Tranzscheliella* comprises 17 species (Vánky 2012).

Whereas species of *Tranzscheliella* occur on members of several subfamilies of *Poaceae* (mainly on *Pooideae*, but also on *Arundinoideae*, *Chloridoideae* and *Panicoideae*, not on *Bambusoideae*), *Bambusiomyces* is restricted to host plants in the tribe *Bambuseae* of the subfam. *Bambusoideae*.

Molecular phylogenetic analyses of several *Tranzscheliella*, including also *T. williamsii* (Begerow *et al.* 2007; Diagne-Leye

et al. 2010), show a separate position from the true *Ustilago* species (type *U. hordei* (Pers. : Pers.) Lagerh.).

Re-examination of the isotype of *U. shiraiana* (HUV 16635) revealed that two additional fungi are present: a smut fungus forming spore balls (attributed earlier to insect frass; shown in Vánky 2012: 1267) and also a hyperparasite with large groups of hyaline conidia.

Spore size, given in the literature, may vary considerably between specimens examined and also within the same specimen. In HUV 21413 (on "*Bambusaceae*", Japan, Miyagi Pref., Sendai-shi, 12.VI.1995, coll. M. Nemoto), the spore length was between 5.5 and 11 μ m.

Fig. 6. Germinating spores of *Bambusiomyces shiraianus* (after Hino 1961: 228, Fig. 134)

Regarding spore germination, there is a striking difference between *Bambusiomyces* and *Tranzscheliella* (comp. Fig. 6 with those of Figs 7–8). In contrast to the short holobasidium with a few, large apical basidiospores in *Bambusiomyces*, in species of *Tranzscheliella* germination results in a septate, often ramifying basidium, on which lateral and terminal, ovoid or ellipsoidal basidiospores are produced on sterigmata, or after fusion of two basidial cells, dikaryotic infection hyphae develop (Figs 7–8; Fischer & Hirschhorn, 1945a: 16 & 20, 1945b: 243, 254, 261).

Spore germination of *Ustilago shiraiana*, illustrated by Hori (1907, Plate XII), shows variations, which are attributed to environmental conditions, e.g. culture media used by Hori (distilled water, “ame-solution”, “modified Cohn solution”), temperature, light, electromagnetic radiation, etc.

Spore germination in smut fungi rarely provides reliable characters for classification at the generic or higher levels, but there are exceptions. Good examples are *Entorrhiza* C.A. Weber (*Entorrhizaceae*), and *Mycosyrinx* Beck (*Mycosyringaceae*) (comp. Fineran 1982; Piepenbring & Bauer 1995; Vánky 1996; Bauer *et al.* 1997).

For a more natural classification of the smut fungi, morphological characters of young sori, spores (spore balls, sterile cells), spore development, and spore germination (basidia, basidiospores, hyphae) should be combined with molecular biological analyses. Unfortunately, several attempts to extract DNA from *B. shiraianus* have failed and its phylogenetic position is still not known.

Fig. 7. Germinating spores of *Tranzscheliella halophyla* (Speg.) Vánky on *Distichlis stricta* (Torr.) Rydb. (after Fischer & Hirschhorn 1945a: 16, Fig. 2C; 1945b: 254, Fig. 4B)

Fig. 8. Germinating spores of *Tranzscheliella williamsii* (Griff.) Dingley & Versluys on *Stipa* (after Fischer & Hirschhorn 1945b: 254, Fig. 4D)

Regarding the economic importance of the stem smut of bamboo, Patterson & Charles (1916: 355) wrote: “In Japan this disease is extremely serious and of great economic importance to the bamboo grower, as it may lead to the death of the entire forest.” Mordue (1991: 64) wrote that infection is commonly restricted, and of local economic importance.

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